

**OPTOELECTRONIC SYSTEM FOR MONITORING OIL CONTENT IN PURIFIED
WATER BASED ON THE ELEMENT OF DISTURBED TOTAL INTERNAL
REFLECTION**

Alijanov Donyorbek Dilshodovich

Dean of the Faculty of Energetics of Andijan
Machine-building Institute

Islomov Doniyorbek Davronbekovich

Phd student of Andijan Machine-building Institute
E-mail:islomov_0303@mail.ru,

Abstract: *Currently , one of the most important problems of oil refineries is determining the presence of oil and oil impurities in running water. This scientific master's thesis of mine is based on these problems of oil refining industries. In the master's thesis, first of all, we set up a task where an optical sensor will be used for oil refining production. Therefore, we focused on the oil refining industry and at this point in the oil refining industry, what methods are used to displace oil from running water. Now it is important to apply spectrometry for used water in the processing of oil in production. And so the problem statement in this method is that how to determine and control running water for oil content. This master's thesis also provides an overview of new scientific publications and works.*

The proposed optoelectronic sensor operates on the basis of a disturbed total internal reflection (LSE) and we will discuss this in detail in our master's thesis.

Keywords: *sensor, cylinder, prisms, master generator (pulse power source), trigger with counting input, light-emitting diodes (LED) and compensation LED, measuring and compensation, optical radiation receivers (POI), adder photoelectric signal processing unit and recording device or computer.*

The main part: Currently, the main sources of oil and petroleum products pollution worldwide are mining enterprises, pumping and transportation systems, oil terminals and oil depots, oil product storage facilities, rail transport, river and offshore oil tankers, gas stations and stations. The sources of pollution are considered to be oil-containing drains that come out of oil-processing industries, causing global harm to our surrounding nature. When choosing a method and equipment for solving the analytical problem of monitoring oil content in purified water, an ultra-sensitive express method for analysis should be used mainly. Currently, the oil industry has dozens of methods and hundreds of devices based on them for determining petroleum products in purified water, which are accepted in various standardization systems: ASTM, EN ISO, IP, GOST. It is also relevant to consider the existing analytical methods for determining petroleum products in purified water in Russia, the results and conclusions of research works performed in the USA and Europe, which were obtained by various existing analytical methods in interlaboratory tests. However, currently in the oil and oil refining industry, even in oil production, there are no express analyzers for determining petroleum products in purified water. Optoelectronic control methods have received a new qualitative change due to the development of optoelectronics. The main elements of devices and devices operating on this principle are semiconductor emitters and receivers-LEDS, photoresistors, phototransistors, photodiodes, photodetectors - these elements have minimal dimensions, high sensitivity, and low power consumption, which makes it possible to create **reliable**, sensitive optoelectronic devices for monitoring and measuring.

Currently, semiconductor emitting diodes are widely used to create optoelectronic devices. Compared to other types of emitters, LED has a number of advantages such as low energy consumption, small dimensions and weight, the ability to withstand significant mechanical overloads, high stability and reliability in operation, high speed, easy radiation modulation, linearity of light characteristics

with functional modulation. These advantages of LEDS allow them to be used as a source of analyzing radiation in primary measuring transducers .

Sensors – based on NIP

The NIP method (Fig. 1) is based on the phenomenon of penetration of a light wave into an optically less dense medium n_2 , when the light flux propagates from an optically denser medium n_1 to a less dense n_2 at an angle.

Figure 1-Physical basis of the NIP method

The physical meaning is as follows. Two light streams with different wavelengths are used, for example, $\lambda_1 = 1.93$ microns (measuring) and $\lambda_2 = 1.7$ microns (reference), corresponding to the maximum and minimum water absorption. The light flux $F_{0\lambda}$ propagates from an optically dense medium with a refractive n_{index} of n_1 to a less dense one with n_2 at an angle Θ exceeding the limit (critical) angle of total internal reflection Θ_k . The luminous flux $F_{0\lambda_1}$ partially penetrates the medium n_2 ; to a depth of the order of the incident radiation wavelength:

$$d_p = \frac{\lambda_1}{2\pi(\sin^2 \Theta - n_{21})^{1/2}} \tag{1}$$

where λ_1 is the wavelength of radiation in an optically dense medium with a refractive index of n_1 ; $n_{21} = n_2/n_1$ is the relative refractive index. If the radiation angle is equal to or exceeds the critical $\Theta_k = \arcsin n_1/n_2$, then total internal reflection is observed (PVO method). Since a less dense medium with a complex refractive $\tilde{n} = n_2 - j\chi_2$ index: has absorption, the reflection will not be complete, i.e. the conditions for this are violated and the reflection coefficient ($R = F_{\lambda_1} / F_{0\lambda_1}$) will become less than 1. The degree of attenuation of R is proportional to the absorption index [1]. Thus, the higher the absorption, the more reflection is disturbed. This is called the NIP effect. In the IR region of the spectrum, in order to achieve the condition n_1 is greater than n_2 , LSE measuring elements made of highly refractive optical materials that are transparent in the corresponding range are used.

They are made mainly in the form of prefixes (called "NIPO prefixes") to various serial spectrometers and spectrophotometers, where the prefixes are installed in the cuvette compartment between the illuminator and the monochromator. Prefixes are available in two versions: with a single reflection or with multiple reflection (MNPVO prefixes). The first ones are designed for obtaining single reflection spectra with the possibility of a smooth change in the angle of incidence and are mainly used for research purposes to determine optical constants of media. MNPVO prefixes allow obtaining spectra with a large number of reflections and a limited number of fixed angles of incidence; they are mainly used for solving analytical problems. Prefixes of NIPO (fig. 2) are issued according to two standard schemes. Scheme a) is the simplest, since it uses only flat mirrors and a simple prismatic element of the NIP. Changing the angle of incidence is performed by turning the NIP element, as well as by turning and moving the mirrors linearly (using a parallelogram mechanism). The NIP element in this prefix is illuminated convergently ($\approx 5^\circ$ aperture) Therefore, it is far from

parallel; the exact setting of the angle of incidence is also difficult due to the different refraction of the beam on the flat surfaces of the element when the angle of incidence changes.

- a) - prismatic: 1-3-flat mirrors; 4-NIP element;
 b) – semi-cylindrical: 1, 5-flat mirrors; 2, 4-toroidal mirrors; 3-element of the NIPO.

Figure 2-NIP prefixes

Scheme b) with a semi-cylindrical NIP element is more advanced, since it provides a light beam close to parallel inside the element, but is somewhat more complex in design. In it, mirrors 1 and 2 are stationary, and the angle of incidence is changed by turning the NIP 3 element around its axis and the corresponding rotation by twice the angle of the mirror 4 and rotation by a small angle of the mirror 5. The interaction of these rotations is made using special cams.

NPVO prefixes are produced in Russia (model NPVO-1, built according to scheme b), as well as by a number of foreign companies. In all known NIPO consoles, the error in setting the angle of incidence is 10-30', and the deviation from the parallelism of the beam inside the element, even in the best consoles

with a semi-cylindrical element and with special adjustment – is not less than 30'. The LSE method is usually unsuitable for studying materials with a highly variable refractive index (for example, quartz). In these cases, it is not possible to maintain the angle of incidence above the critical one over the entire wavelength range.

Despite these drawbacks, in many cases the NIP method has expanded the scope of optical spectroscopy and simplified the measurement procedure, in particular the sample preparation procedure. As a confirmation of this, we point out that it is easy to obtain the NIPO spectra of powders. Another important advantage of the LSE method is the absence of interference fringes in the spectrum. The fields of application of optical spectroscopy have significantly expanded due to the new opportunity to obtain the LSE spectra of objects without destroying the latter (for example, the spectra of films on absorbing substrates, fibers, fabrics, samples deposited on filter paper, etc.). Another advantage of the LSE method over the transmission method, which is not yet fully used, is the presence of reflection of electric fields on the surface. fields in all three spatial directions, which is important in the study of anisotropic materials. Apparently, the most important area of application of LSE spectroscopy is the rapid analysis of oil and petroleum products.

conclusion: The progress made in the development of optoelectronic sensors for the oil industry in recent years is very significant. First of all, we should mention such areas as level measurement, phase separation, alarm of emergency level and leaks from pipelines and storage facilities, pressure, temperature and density measurements, determination of the chemical composition of petroleum products.

list of literature

1. Alijanov, D. D., & Axmadaliyev, U. A. (2021). APV Receiver In Automated Systems. The American Journal of Applied sciences.
2. Muhiddin Qodirjonovich Shamshiddinov, Oybek Bakhtiyorjon ogli Parpiev Use Of Electronic Keys To Increase Energy Savings Of Led Lights // The American Journal of Applied sciences IMPACT FACTOR 2021: 5. 634
3. Dilshodovich, A. D., & Rakhimovich, R. N. (2020). Optoelectronic Method for Determining the Physicochemical Composition of Liquids. *Автоматика и программная инженерия*, (2 (32)), 51-53.
4. Ларина, Т. В., Кутенкова, Е. Ю., Жмудь, В. А., & Алижанов, Д. Д. (2012). Оптоэлектронный метод контроля физико-механических параметров поверхностей твердых материалов. *Автоматика и программная инженерия*, (1 (1)), 43-48.
5. Ларина, Т. В., Рахимов, Н. Р., & Алижанов, Д. Д. (2012). Разработка оптоэлектронного датчика для исследования процесса усталости образца металлических конструкций. *Автоматика и программная инженерия*, (2 (2)), 31-35.
6. Alijanov, D. D., & Boltaboyev, I. M. (2021). Receiver For Registration Of X-Ray And Ultraviolet Radiation. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(03), 23-27.
7. Alijanov, D. D., & Axmadaliyev, U. A. (2020). The Peculiarities Of Automatic Headlights. The American Journal of Engineering and Technology.
8. Photosensitive sensors in automated systems / Alijanov D.D., Boltaboyev I.M. // PHOTONSENSITIVE SENSORS IN AUTOMATED SYSTEMS // Internauka: elektron. nauchn. журн. 2020. № 23(152).
9. D.D.Alijanov, N.Rakhimov. (2020). Optoelectronic Method for Determining the Physicochemical Composition of Liquids . *Automatics & Software Enginery*, 51-53.

10. Lisovskii V. V. Teoriya i praktika sverhvysokofchastnogo kontrolya soglasnosti sel'skikh materialov [Theory and practice of ultrahigh-frequency humidity control of agricultural materials].
11. Rakhimov N. R., Alizhanov D. D. Features of obtaining a coordinate-чувствительного sensitive optical radiation receiver based on semiconductor films with anomalous photovoltage. [Log].
12. Topvoldiyev, N. (2022). PHYSICAL AND TECHNICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF PHOTOELECTRIC SOLAR PANELS ENERGY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*.
13. Topvoldiyev, N. (2023). *Quyosh havo isitish kollektorlarini o`rnatish va foydalaniz*.
14. ME Yulchiev, AAO Qodirov Electricity Quality And Power Consumption In Low Power (0.4 Kv) Networks, THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY (TAJET) SJIF-5.32 DOI-10.37547/tajet
15. NM Aripov, OA Qosimov MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH 2 ...